

METHODS OF DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENTS DURING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: In order to further improve the quality of education in developing Uzbekistan, it is necessary to teach young students to develop their critical thinking, to enrich their knowledge from a young age, to develop independent thinking and free creativity. It is necessary to emphasize that the role and importance of critical thinking in personal development is incomparable.

Key words: students-youth, critical thinking, critical analysis, self-control, formation, development, free creativity.

Introduction.

Today, all areas of the life of New Uzbekistan have become a field of deep reforms. In this process, it is impossible not to talk excitedly about the changes in the education system, which is considered the basis of the social sphere. In recent years, in our country, practical work on the organization of all stages of the education system based on modern requirements has entered a decisive stage. Reforms aimed at raising the quality and content of education to a new level, developing a new mechanism for training qualified personnel, and updating educational programs and literature are being implemented step by step.

The purpose of the study. Nowadays, in order to contribute to the development of our country, by studying in our educational institutions with the content of Eastern education, the young generation who are growing up should learn independent critical thinking, as emphasized by Khorezmi, Farobi, Ibn Sina, who are representatives of the East. To teach and to show that the knowledge acquired as a result has a great advantage in the development of the society has an important place in the process of today's globalization.

Therefore, when this knowledge is developed more fully and quickly in students, it becomes a belief and is a tool for their thinking and active practical critical thinking. In particular, the president of our country touches on this issue through the following points: critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activity. Scientists, pedagogues, psychologists and methodologists are engaged. In particular, in the works of V.V.Davidov, M.G.Davletshin, I.Y.Lerner, A.M.Matyushkin, M.I.Mahmutov, S.Rajabov, D.Shodiyev, A.M.Umronkhojayev, the types of

generalization and their structure in the principles of problem-based education and the organization of the educational process are revealed.

At this point, we express the following thoughts of the Russian writer Tolstoy: "Wisdom is not knowing as much as possible, but knowing what knowledge is most necessary, what is less, and what is extremely necessary." Sociologist and philosopher G. Spencer says: "If a person's knowledge is chaotic, the more knowledge he has, the more chaotic his thoughts become." That is why it is necessary to teach young students to think critically and analyze critically from a young age so that they can become mature cadres of our country in the future.

Research tasks. What is critical thinking? Critical thinking is a special type of thinking, which draws conclusions by analyzing facts. Critical thinking is a form of self-directed, self-educated, self-controlled, self-correcting thinking. Its prerequisite is to agree to strict standards of consciousness improvement and to apply them with vigilance. Critical thinking requires effective communication and problem-solving skills. A person with critical thinking skills has the ability to think logically and well-founded.

The term critical thinking is used in the International Terminology System (Greek) as a critical form of thinking and comes from the multi-meaning word "criticism", "evaluation", "examination" (etc.): here the concept of criticism is used in everyday life. does not mean "blame" but means mental ability and has meanings such as "assess", "determine", "judge", "distinguish". The intellectual foundations of critical thinking, as well as its etymology, go back to very ancient times, that is, it is possible to find content close to this concept in the teaching practice and thoughts of Socrates 2500 years ago. After that, in the natural and scientific works of medieval thinkers who lived and created in the Near and Middle East, we can see that there is a serious interest in various aspects of science, its principles, structure, criteria, and the connection of science with human mental development and critical thinking.

Research results and its discussion. The bud of the theory of thinking arose with the emergence of science and continues to develop. The content of critical thinking is connected through three external factors: its object, its purpose, and the laws of the development of didactic foundations. By the external side of critical thinking, we understand the stimulation of much simpler processes and the maintenance of the student's general working ability. The following methods are used for this:

- To ensure the replacement of work of different nerve centers by alternating different methods, types and methods of educational work;
- The correct interaction of words and visuality, concrete and abstract in the educational process;
- Minutes of physical and musical rest in the lesson;
- Support of positive emotions;
- Using games and competitions as a didactic method.

The inner side of critical thinking is primarily to activate students' thinking, and in primary groups, to stimulate their imagination and creativity. The main methods used for the purposes of the internal side of the formation of critical thinking are as follows:

- Independent work of students;
- Elements of self- and mutual control;
- A problem-based approach to the education of future primary school teachers;
- Elements of the adaptation system of education and others.

Critical thinking is described by Richard W. Paul as a two-wave movement (1994). The "first wave" of critical thinking is often called "critical analysis," pure, rational thinking that includes criticism. Its details vary among those who refer to it. According to Barry K. Beyer (1995), critical thinking means making clear, reasoned judgments. In the process of critical thinking, ideas must be proven, fully considered, and evaluated. The US National Council on Critical Thinking Skills defines critical thinking as "the active and skillful transformation, application, analysis, synthesis, or application of information gathered or generated through observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication into concepts that guide belief and action (conceptualization). is defined as an intellectual, progressive process of assessment.

Contemporary critical thinking scholars have attempted to expand these traditional definitions to include qualities, concepts, and processes, including creativity, imagination, inquiry, excitement, empathy, knowledge linking, feminist theory, subjectivity, uncertainty, and futility. Some definitions of critical thinking exclude these subjective experiences.

According to Ennis, "critical thinking is the intellectual and disciplined process of conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information gathered or generated through observation, experience, reflection,

study, or association that guides belief and action. This definition of Ennis is based on Harvey Siegel, Submitted by Peter Fazione and Deanna Kuhn.

According to Ennis, critical thinking requires focus and brain activity. If critical thinking is included in the educational field, this method increases the brain activity of the students and helps them to understand the texts in a different way.

Developing critical thinking is not an easy task. It is not a task that is completed and forgotten at a certain age. To learn critical thinking, one must care about everything. There are many unlearned things in life. Curiosity develops intelligence. Through curiosity, discoveries and adventures take place, and as a result, a person's critical thinking develops and makes his life colorful. In addition, there is a set of specific educational conditions that help the formation of critical thinkers. They are as follows:

- Creating time and opportunities for students to think;
- Accepting different ideas and opinions;
- Ensuring students' activity in the educational process;
- Convince students not to laugh;
- To instill a sense of confidence in the ability of every student to think critically;
- Critical thinking should be appreciated.

In this regard, students should gain self-confidence and understand the value of their thoughts and ideas; active participation in the educational process; listen carefully to different opinions; it is necessary to be ready to form one's own judgments and to return from them.

The first step in developing critical thinking is daily analysis. At the end of the day, it is necessary to weigh and study the progress made during the day. The number of missed ones should also be taken into account. The analysis should consist of identifying the actions in which mistakes were made in the process of execution. You need to identify the shortcomings of the previous day and think about how to eliminate them. In the end, it is necessary to conclude whether the event has moved closer to the goal or moved away from it. Based on these simple actions, thinking develops, which later turns into critical thinking. The second step in developing critical thinking is to think critically. If they cause unwanted consequences, they are worth considering. Try to think positively and avoid negative thoughts. Because one must learn: One who decides to develop critical thinking must draw a line between conclusions and observations. You can't argue without verifying the data. You can draw conclusions only if you

have specific information. At the same time, you need to ensure that you do not lose your sense of humor during training. The ability to joke with oneself and see the humor in situations helps to maintain a clear mind and freely express one's opinion on a problem. But if laughter is used as a psychological defense, one should be careful.

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